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EFFECTS OF PSYCHOEDUCATION ON ATTITUDES AND BELIEFS OF PATIENTS WITH UNIPOLAR DEPRESSION TOWARDS ANTI-DEPRESSANT THERAPY

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to provide psychoeducation for changing the attitudes and beliefs of patients with unipolar depression towards antidepressant treatment. The study was a prospective, comparative, randomized, interventional study conducted at psychiatry Out-patient Department in a Tertiary Care Hospital, Guntur which includes 89 patients with unipolar depression. Those patients who are receiving psychoeducation along with antidepressant treatment are randomized into study group where as those patients only on antidepressant therapy are grouped as control. The data was collected through Antidepressant Compliance Questionnaire at base level and after 2 months, where the study group received 3 sessions of psychoeducation with 15 days time interval between each session. Among 89 patients who participated in study, 08 could not be followed up in the study, hence dropped out. Out of 81 patients 38.2% were male and 61.7% were female. Majority of patients 44.4% were in the age group between 40 to 50 years and 87.6% of patients with 10th and below 10th educational status were found to have depression. Patient doctor relationship (Component 1 of ADCQ) had correlation of (r=0.68, p=0.0001) and have positive correlation with follow up (r=0.76, p=0.0001). The correlation is not significant at p=0.05. Correlation between positive belief on antidepressant (Component 3 of ADCQ) and follow up scores after psychoeducation (r=0.999, p=0.0001) which is significant at p=0.01. Correlation between partner's agreement (Component 4 of ADCQ) and follow up scores after psychoeducation (r=0.96, p=0.009) which is significant at p=0.05. By this we conclude that psychoeducation improves the attitudes and beliefs of the patients with unipolar depression towards antidepressants and its main outcome is based on the patient doctor relationship where the sufficient time should be spent on the patient towards their feelings.

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INTRODUCTION

“Depression is a common mental disorder that presents with depressed mood, loss of interest or pleasure, decreased energy, feelings of guilt or low self-worth, disturbed sleep or appetite, and poor concentration” [1]. The World Health Organization has ranked depression the 4th leading cause of disability worldwide. Attitude, is explained as a mental position with regard to a faith or a fact [2]. Beliefs can be defined as a probable characteristic of a concept [3]. A large number of patients with depression have incorrect and negative views not only toward antidepressants but depression itself [4]. The most common misperception among these patients is that depression is caused only by non-biological or environmental factors, such as stress or family problems [5]. Patients also believe that antidepressants are addictive [6] that they can alter the patient’s personality, [7] that fewer tablets can be taken on days when one feels better, and that extra tablets can be taken on days when they feel depressed [7]. A significantly negative correlation has been found between patient attitudes and beliefs toward depression and antidepressants and the percentage of days medication was missed. Therefore, subjects with negative attitudes missed their medications more frequently [7]. In fact, research has shown that compared to side effects and patients’ beliefs about a disease and its perceived controllability or consequences had a greater influence on patient adherence rates [7].

According to the World Health Organization, depression is one of the most frequent of all medical illnesses [8]. At its worst, depression can lead to suicide, a tragic fatality accompanying the loss of about 850 000 lives every year [9]. Considering the patients who do receive treatment and are prescribed antidepressants, 50% to 83% either discontinue their medication prematurely or take it too inconsistently to derive any clinical results [10-12]. Beliefs and attitudes are often neglected in research, as they are complex and ambivalent [13]. Since the evidence does not provide a conclusive picture on beliefs and attitudes [14], it has been difficult to detect structures or dimensions in patient beliefs and attitudes towards antidepressants in a reliable way [15].

The areas studied have been the aetiology of depression, the usefulness of treatments, the search for help and the perceived stigma. Beliefs about the causes of depression are mostly non-biological, psychological or environmental [16]. The most commonly mentioned causes of depression were stress associated with work, followed by personality and family situation, with only 3.6% of the respondents giving biological reasons [17]. Beliefs about the causes of depression influence patient treatment preferences, as well as their assignment to treatment or another. The preference for psychotherapy is associated with attribution of the aetiology to problems in childhood and to more complex aetiologies, compared to patients who prefer drug treatment [18].

The main negative beliefs about antidepressants are addictive possibilities (especially in males), over medication and prescription abuse of antidepressants [19]. Adolescents preferred psychotherapy over drugs, and the main adverse effects that would make adherence to antidepressant treatment difficult for them were the increase of weight for girls and the sexual effects for boys [20]. Preferring psychotherapy to drugs is consistently established in studies of patients with depression, primary care patients and the general population [16]. The factors associated with this preference include female sex, greater knowledge of psychotherapy or previous experience with it, paid time off and not having been recently treated with antidepressants. Patients in serious condition also perceive the usefulness of pharmacological and psychotherapeutic co-therapy, from which they can learn coping mechanisms and change their thinking patterns, patterns of coping with stress and difficult relationships [16].

In order to explain what underlies antidepressant beliefs [21] associated a rational and limited set of variables with patient beliefs towards antidepressants. A multivariate regression analysis indicated that the necessity beliefs (perceived need for antidepressant medication) were higher for patients with older age, greater symptom severity, the expectation that the symptoms will last a long time and that the symptoms are caused by biochemical factors. Other indicators that are traditionally associated with poor depression outcomes, such as psychiatric co-morbidity, age at first episode and melancholic or anxious depression were unrelated to perceived necessity. Harmfulness beliefs were stronger endorsed by patients who had never taken antidepressants before, patients who believed that symptoms were randomly caused and patients who lack a clear notion of their symptoms [22].

A collaborative approach requires that the physician clearly communicates with the patient on the use of antidepressants; what to take, how much and when to take. The communication concerning the use should be accompanied by a general idea of how the medication works and discussion of potential side effects and ways to alleviate these side effects. Additionally, the physician should indicate when one can expect to begin feeling better, including expected length of treatment. Through path analysis the authors further showed that physician’s initial collaborative communication style predicts besides better patients’ knowledge of the medication regimen also more positive initial patients’ beliefs towards antidepressants and a follow-up with the physician in collaborative communication style. Patients’ knowledge of the medication regimen predicts patients’ satisfaction with antidepressants. Patients’ satisfaction is also predicted by more positive initial beliefs towards antidepressants and by a collaborative follow-up with the physician. The latter is also predicted by the initial beliefs towards antidepressants. Patients’ satisfaction with antidepressants is predictive of fewer medication omissions, just as a collaborative follow-up style by the physician [23].

Figure.1 Path analysis of effects of physician communication style on patient beliefs. Adapted from Bultman & Svarstad [23].

Figure 2 Reasons for Non-adherence to antidepressants.

Measuring and monitoring adherence is an important aspect of effective care. Several methods were developed to measure adherence to medication and psychotropic drugs. Traditionally the main methods used to measure adherence among outpatients include using pharmacy refill records and by following the drop-outs versus completers with electronic monitoring and the frequency of failure to take antidepressants by examining self reported medication adherence. Also adherence is assessed more objectively for research purposes, based on the medication possession ratio, which was estimated as the proportion of days for which medication was available over each period of follow-up. A self report scale may help improve accuracy. The advantage of the interview and self reporting method however include its feasibility in all care settings, simplicity, and speed especially when administering a brief adherence self report instrument. This also will allow establishing a positive therapeutic rapport between the patients and prescribers [24].

Psychoeducation is a general term for an educational approach of assistance to offer accurate knowledge and information about the nature and methods of treatment and addressing the disease needed for cure added with consideration for psychotherapy. In the background of why psychoeducation is now regarded important is that litigations against the unilateral treatment provided by medical profession have increased. As abundance of medical information passes to the patient side, it is difficult and often chaotic to understand and deal with them adequately. A study on how the family expresses emotion influences prognosis of mental disorder suggests the importance of understanding of the disease by the family and closed. This means not only the unilateral offering of information from the medical service provider but also removing misunderstandings of the disease, improving cognition, and evaluating the manner of addressing problems surrounding the disease. Thus, it is called psycho-education, not mere education. The objects are not limited to psychiatry patients but include those suffering from cancer, AIDS, and the sequel of strokes. The important thing is that the treatment is performed not by the top-down method of doctor to patient, but by cooperation with the patient and the family [25].

AIM

The study aim is to provide psychoeducation for changing the attitudes and beliefs and improving the quality of life of patients with unipolar depression towards antidepressant treatment.

OBJECTIVES:

- To assess the attitudes and beliefs of patients with Unipolar depression towards antidepressant treatment.
- To evaluate the Quality of life of patients with Unipolar depression.
- To evaluate the effect of psycho education on above parameters in patient's with Unipolar depression.

MATERIALS & METHODS:**Study Design:**

Prospective, comparative, randomized, interventional study.

Study sample:

89 patients with unipolar depression.

Sampling Technique:

89 patients were randomized into Study group and Control group.

Drop outs:

8

Study Duration:

6 months (i.e., Jan' 2016- June' 2016).

Study place:

Government General Hospital, Guntur,

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Patients with unipolar depression.
- Age group:18-50 years
- Patients willing to come for regular follow-up
- Patients who give written informed consent.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- The patients with severe depressive illness with psychotic features and severe agitation were excluded.
- Patients with other known psychiatric illness.
- Patients with medical co-morbidities and pregnant women.

METHODOLOGY

A Prospective, comparative, randomized, interventional study was conducted on subjects with unipolar depression. The subjects were recruited based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria includes those patients suffering with unipolar depression, belonging to Age group 18-50 years, willing to come for regular follow-up and patients who had given written informed consent. Exclusion criteria includes patients with severe depressive illness with psychotic features and severe agitation, with other known psychiatric illness and Patients with medical co-morbidities and pregnant women. The study was conducted in 4 phases: In phase 1 initially the socio-demographic data was collected, attitudes and beliefs of patients with unipolar depression were assessed through Anti depressant compliance questionnaire (ADCQ). ADCQ consists of 33 questions of which 1-15 questions represents Patient-Doctor Relationship, 16-22 represents perceived autonomy, 23-30 represents positive beliefs on depression towards antidepressant therapy and 31-33 on partner's agreement. In phase 2 patients were randomized based on those receiving psychoeducation along with antidepressant therapy as study group, where as those receiving antidepressant alone were chosen as control group. Both study group as well as control group were expected for regular follow up. In phase 3 psychoeducation was provided for 3 sessions (for every 15 days) followed by attitudes and beliefs of patients was assessed through ADCQ. In final phase the collected data was analyzed and results were tabulated. Statistical analysis was performed using paired t-test and independent t-test by SPSS VERSION 19.0.

RESULTS:

SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC PARAMETERS:

PATIENT CHARACTERISTICS.

Parameter	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
10-20	04	4.9%
21-30	12	14.8%
31-40	29	35.8%
41-50	36	44.5%
Gender		
Male	31	38.3%
Female	50	61.7%
Employment		
Employed	46	58.6%
Unemployed	35	43.2%
Education		
10 th or below 10 th	71	87.7%
Intermediate	06	7.4%
Degree and above	04	4.9%

Age wise distribution:

Figure.3 Age wise distribution.

On the basis of age wise distribution, depression patients are more in age ranging between 41-50 years and this is less in age group of 18-30 years.

GENDER WISE DISTRIBUTION:

Figure.4 Gender wise distribution.

On the basis of gender wise distribution, depression patients are more in female category than in male category.

Educational status:

Figure.5: Educational status.

Based on the educational status the patients with depression were found to be in below 10th class and 10th class than compared to degree and above educated people who are said to be less significant to the disease.

Occupational status:

Figure.6 Occupational status.

Based on the occupational status, the depression was found to be more in case of employed subjects compared to unemployed subjects.

Marital status:

Figure.7 Marital status.

Based on the marital status, the depression was found to be more in case of married subjects compared to unmarried subjects.

Component 1: Patient doctor relationship

Figure.8 ADCQ Component 1 control group.

Figure.9ADCQ Component 1 Study group.

Table 1: Comparison between ADCQ Component 1 control group and study group.

PARAMETER	Without Psychoeducation	With Psychoeducation
p value	0.0007 ***	0.0001***
r value	0.6807	0.7661
Mean of differences	6.600	14.20
SD of difference	5.950	5.414

Component 2: Percieved autonomy.

Figure.10ADCQ Component 2 control groupFigure. 11 ADCQ Component 2 Study group.

Table 2: Comparison between ADCQ Component 2 control group and study group.

PARAMETER	Without Psychoeducation	With Psychoeducation
p value	0.0096**	0.0005***
r value	0.6509	0.4784
Mean of differences	6.363	10.29
SD of difference	4.503	4.001

Component 3: Positive belief on depression and antidepressant.

Figure.12ADCQ Component 3 control groupFigure. 13 ADCQ Component 3 Study group.

Table 3: Comparison between ADCQ Component 3 control group and study group.

PARAMETER	Without Psychoeducation	With Psychoeducation
p value	0.0007***	0.0001****
r value	0.9966	0.9990
Mean of differences	3.700	6.0000
SD of difference	1.236	0.8944

Component 4: Partner's agreement.

Figure.14 ADCQ Component 4 control group

Figure.15 ADCQ Component 4 Study group.

Table 4: Comparison between ADCQ Component 4 control group and study group.

PARAMETER	Without Psychoeducation	With Psychoeducation
p value	0.1149	0.0096
r value	0.9533	0.9616
Mean of differences	6.167	15.53
SD of difference	3.972	2.656

Among 89 patients who participated in study, 08 could not be followed up in the study and hence dropped out. Out of 81 patients 38.2% were male and 61.7% were female. Majority of patients 44.4% were in the age group between 40 to 50 years and 87.6% of patients with 10th and below 10th educational status were found to have depression.

The mean difference of "Patient doctor relationship" was 6.60 in control group and with psychoeducation is said to be of 14.20. These results showed that patients are satisfied with the doctor. The mean difference of "Perceived autonomy" is 6.36 in control group and with psychoeducation is said to be of 10.29. The mean difference of "positive belief on depression and antidepressant" is 3.70 in control group and with psychoeducation is said to be 6. The mean difference of "Partner's agreement" is 6.16 in control group and with psychoeducation is said to be 15.53.

Correlation:

Patient doctor relationship (Component 1 of ADCQ) had correlation of ($r=0.68$, $p=0.0001$) and have positive correlation with follow up ($r=0.76$, $p=0.0001$).

The correlation is not significant at $p=0.05$. Correlation between positive belief on antidepressant (Component 3 of ADCQ) and follow up scores after psychoeducation ($r=0.999$, $p=0.0001$) which is significant at $p=0.01$. Correlation between partner's agreement (Component 4 of ADCQ) and follow up scores after psychoeducation ($r=0.96$, $p=0.009$) which is significant at $p=0.05$.

DISCUSSION

Based on the data obtained the results reveal that majority of the study population age, gender, educational status, occupational status, marital status were found to be 41-50 yrs (44.4%) , females (61.8%), tenth & below tenth (87.7%), employed (58.6%) and married (55.5%) respectively, which also shows that majority of them has 1st visited the traditional practices to cure depression which many of them don't know about the psychiatric treatment and psychoeducation which made a drastic change in their life style after coming to the Psychiatric treatment and attending the psychoeducation sessions.

The mean score of "Patient doctor relationship" is 6.60 that shows the patients rather agree on this. These results showed that patients are satisfied with the doctor. 79.8% of patients agreed doctors gave sufficient time to listen and discuss their problems, the mean score of "Patient doctor relationship" was 14.20 that shows the patients rather agree on this. These results showed that patients are satisfied with the doctor. The mean score of "Perceived autonomy" is 10.29 that shows the patients rather disagree on this. The mean score of "positive belief on depression and antidepressant" is 6.0. The mean score of "Partner's agreement" is 15.53.

Patient doctor relationship (Component 1 of ADCQ) have positive correlation with follow up ($r=0.68$, $p=0.0001$). Correlation between positive belief on antidepressant (Component 3 of ADCQ) and follow up scores ($r=0.999$, $p=0.0001$). Correlation between partner's agreement (Component 4 of ADCQ) and follow up scores after counseling ($r=0.96$, $p=0.009$).

CONCLUSION

By observing the study we conclude that psychoeducation improves the attitudes and beliefs of the patients with unipolar depression towards antidepressants. By using Antidepressant compliance questionnaire we not only assessed the compliance of the patients but we also assessed their attitudes and beliefs towards anti-depressants and also towards depression, psychoeducation plays a key role to improve positive results in all the components of the Antidepressant compliance questionnaire.

Bottom Line:

We can perform a innovative study whether the effect of psychoeducation can improve the quality of life of the patients with unipolar depression towards anti-depressant therapy.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ADCQ - ANTIDEPRESSANT COMPLIANCE QUESTIONNAIRE

WHO - WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION

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